

Intelligent Control of Bi-directional Converter for Solar Energy System Using TS-Fuzzy logic

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Abstract

This paper proposes a battery management system with PV array. The topology consists of solar energy as an input sources and a battery bank to store the converted energy when it is in excess. The array is equipped with DC/DC boost convertor, whereas the battery management system (BMS) is connected with bi-directional DC/DC convertor. The bi-directional converter provides required power flow for charging - discharging to battery. The charging-discharging of battery is optimized using BMS at different conditions. To extract the maximum power from the solar array the Perturb & Observe method (P&O), Incremental conductance (INC) and TS-Fuzzy techniques are used. According to the different MPPT technique the characteristics of photovoltaic array is also changed in the presence of various circumstances. According to the changes of PV voltage and current the output power is also change, therefore the BMS starts. Objective of paper is that it deals with various MPPT techniques. We propose P&O, incremental conductance and TS-Fuzzy controller for MPPT technique in PV array. The obtained results are compared to find the effectiveness of system and in battery management system (BMS).